

Supplementary Figure S1: Full Search Strategy

Keywords used in database literature searches

Concept 1: Injectable Hydrogels

- 1) Hydrogels [A1]
- 2) Extracellular matrix hydrogels [B1]
- 3) Tissue engineering [C1]

Concept 2:

- 1) Myocardial infarction [A2]

Concept 3: Myocardial restoration therapy

- 1) Myocardial infarction therapy [A3]
- 2) Cardiac stem cell therapy [B3]
- 3) Cell-based therapy [C3]

Table S1: Number of Results Retrieved with Each Permutation of Key Words

Permutation	Key Word	Number of search results		
		PubMed	Embase	Web of Science
A1A2	Hydrogels AND Myocardial infarction	453	277	25
A1A3	Hydrogels AND Myocardial Infarction Therapy	370	158	1
A1B3	Hydrogels AND Cardiac stem cell therapy	206	134	2
A1C3	Hydrogels AND Cell-based therapy	455	197	10
B1A2	Extracellular matrix hydrogels AND Myocardial infarction	78	49	0
B1A3	Extracellular matrix hydrogels AND Myocardial infarction therapy	62	29	0
B1B3	Extracellular matrix hydrogels AND Cardiac stem cell therapy	45	37	0
B1C3	Extracellular matrix hydrogels AND Cell-based therapy	88	51	0
C1A2	Tissue engineering AND Myocardial infarction	1373	3189	25
C1A3	Tissue engineering AND Myocardial infarction therapy	933	1732	1
C1B3	Tissue engineering AND Cardiac stem cell therapy	1081	1998	6
C1C3	Tissue engineering AND Cell-based therapy	2742	3139	32
A2B3	Myocardial infarction AND Cardiac stem cell therapy	3324	4888	39
A2C3	Myocardial infarction AND Cell-based therapy	619	838	18
Total Number of Results Per Database		11829	16716	159
Total Number of Results		28704		